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Tuning synthesis and sonochemistry forges learning and enhances educational training: Protection of 1,3-diols under heterogeneous catalysis as sustainable case study

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Abstract: This research article describes the thermal and sonochemical enhancements of 1,3-diol protection, via acetal formation, catalyzed by a biomass-derived heterogeneous catalyst. This investigation was also conducted under the framework of a postgraduate program in green chemistry, and the application of ultrasonic activation represented an opportunity to expose the field to junior colleagues unaware of sonochemistry. Accordingly, we show not only a facile and high-yielding synthetic transformation, but also the pluses of performing a parallel protocol using low-frequency ultrasound, which provided new learning tools and skills in context. The main role of sound waves can be associated to enhanced mass transfer of the heterogeneous reaction (*false sonochemistry*). Acoustic energy was delivered into the reagents and solvent using so-called *cavitation intensifying bags* (CIB). The micropitted polymeric material enabled a greater focused radiation that proved to be highly reproducible at 25 °C and led to reaction completion much faster than the conventional external heating. Furthermore, sonication fine-tunes selectivity in ketal formation, as witnessed by a facile synthesis of *solketal*, a green solvent obtained by acetalization of glycerol. The pedagogical benefits of conveying education in sonochemistry are outlined, alongside the catalyst characterization of the ultrasound-driven reaction. Our ambition is to stimulate similar pursuits in synthesis and catalysis at other laboratories and educational institutions.

Keywords: diol protection · heterogeneous catalysis · education in sonochemistry · green chemistry · synthetic sonochemistry · solketal

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and motivation

Merging ultrasound waves and synthetic (organic) chemistry dates back to the early times of sonochemistry, although the ability of ultrasonic irradiation to boost chemical reactivity gained increased attention from the late 1980s onwards [1,2]. The field also meets several green chemistry principles in terms of waste prevention or minimization by virtue of enhanced conversion and selectivity, often associated to acceleration under mild conditions [3–5]. The number of applications in synthesis, catalysis, and materials preparation has grown at an accelerated pace in recent years, and certainly the expeditious access to bioactive and drug-like compounds constitutes a key motivation [6–8]. Even recognizing that most physico-chemical effects arise ultimately from cavitation, sonication seems sometimes to be a method lacking a clear-cut rationale, *a lab trick to ameliorate something*, which contrasts with the emergence of alternative activation strategies like photochemistry or electrochemistry having well-defined mechanisms at atomic and molecular levels. This concern may be detrimental to educational purposes and especially, to convey the heuristic planning from design to target [9].

Adoption of an enabling technology involves a heuristic decision-making process that selects successful reaction conditions for further screening, checking their reproducibility, and assessing the stages where improvements are to be expected [10]. Iterative cycles of synthesis and analysis aided by human input lead eventually to an optimized test. Figure 1 displays a sono-synthesis workflow bearing the above conceptual basis in mind.

Figure 1. Modular workflow and heuristic planning based on specific targets and database or literature searches. Application takes input from analytic measurements. Successful data deemed to be hits are taken forward for reproducibility or scaling-up. Improvements with an enabling technology like ultrasound can be incorporated into the same modules.

The simple modification of an existing method by another ultrasonically-assisted protocol may be unfounded, unless comparative screenings are provided or a distinctive mechanism can be disclosed. Actually, most effects, yet notorious, are largely physical, associated with enhanced mass and energy transfers provided by cavitation collapse and/or streaming, such as those observed in heterogeneous reactions, extraction, crystallization, or structural modifications in (nano)materials. Obviously, they require a careful optimization of experimental parameters, as well as re-assessment of working conditions for process intensification when translating into continuous operations [11]. On the contrary, effects arising directly from *cavitation chemistry*, i.e. direct participation of radical or excited species in reaction outcomes are rare [12]. That said, either heterogeneous reaction could benefit from ultrasonic activation as there are specific steps that can be improved (Figure 2). Thus, a mechanically reluctant reaction could substantially be ameliorated under less heterogeneous conditions that facilitate diffusion and mixing due to interfacial cavitation. Solvents respond differently to cavitation energy, which depends otherwise on vapor pressure and viscosity, among other properties. Likewise, while higher conversions may require extra energy input, selectivity can be fine-tuned by decreasing the acoustic power density (bath vs probes).

Figure 2. Fixing synthesis with sonochemistry. Changes can be made on a range of experimental variables and conditions.

1.2. Research-oriented learning

As continuation on our current endeavors in catalytic developments for functional group manipulations, efforts are addressed towards cheap and readily available biomass-based heterogeneous catalysts, which can in turn be easily separated and recycled. Hydrothermal carbonization allows for more sustainable metal-free catalysts, generated through milder conditions than current pyrolytic processes [13]. Since this investigation involves both senior and junior coworkers entering the sonochemical applications, we foresaw the possibility of developing a research-oriented learning [14,15], which is therefore exposed herein and highlights the pluses of using sonochemistry in both research and education. Under this constructivist approach, the role of ultrasound waves

is best understood, as the conceptual basis takes advantage of a specific molecular mechanism linked to cavitation, which releases mechanical energy in a fluid and provides sufficient rational arguments when compared with a purely thermal activation [16].

The hydrothermal carbons, generated from saccharose, both in pristine and sulfonated forms, have been employed to achieve the protection of functional groups, hydroxyl groups in particular, an indispensable methodology in organic synthesis. Although modern synthesis strives towards processes bypassing the use of protecting groups to shorten stepwise routes and minimizing waste production [17,18], protection and deprotection are usually mandatory as the complexity of the target increases [19]. Protection of OH groups is challenging, not only due to their reactive promiscuity, which makes it difficult selective operations, but also because multiple vicinal OH, either in 1,2 or 1,3-arrangements decorate numerous natural products and drugs. Figure 3 shows some representative examples of bioactive molecules such as a bacterial saccharide (**1**), hyaluronic acid (**2**), heparin (**4**), or ingenol (**3**), the latter mimicking the role of diacylglycerol, the endogenous activator of protein kinase C. Molnupiravir (**5**) is especially appealing, as this modified nucleoside was developed and licensed in less than two years to treat SARS-CoV2 infection. It can be obtained from cytidine with key steps involving acetonide protection and deprotection of vicinal OH groups [20].

The structure of solketal (**6**) is also displayed, as this simple acetonide represents a bio-based green solvent, with major applications on the rise, which also include its use as plasticizer and additive in pharmaceutical formulations [21]. Large-scale solketal production comes from upgrading glycerol, the major residue of biofuel industry, by treatment with acetone using acid conditions, in particular heterogeneous Brønsted acids [22].

The present study explores in detail thermal reactions at different temperatures vis-à-vis the sonochemical protocol performed at ambient conditions at low-frequency irradiation. To this end, an ultrasonic cleaning bath was the set-up of choice, albeit with focused sonication using cavitation bags (see Methods) This set-up allows the use of standard laboratory consumables and conventional glassware, and we found a consistent reproducibility. Importantly, this should permit to share knowledge with other laboratories wishing to pursue similar synthetic transformations and parallel analyses.

Figure 3. Bioactive polyhydroxylated compounds (1-5), whose synthetic preparation demands selective functional group protection/deprotection. Solketal (6), an environmentally friendly solvent, comes from glycerol protection as acetonide.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Analytical and spectroscopic acquisition data

Adsorption of N_2 was performed at 77 K in a Quadrasorb Evo equipment from Quantachrome Instruments, with a previous degasification at 120 °C for 24 h. Elemental analyses were determined on a Leco CHNS-932 analyzer. X-ray fluorescence spectra were recorded on a Bruker S8 Tiger instrument. X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analyses were performed on a FlexPS-ARPES-E equipment from SPECS with monochromatic $K\alpha$ Al radiation, 12 kV voltage, and 6 mA current. Binding energies values were internally referenced to the C1s peak at 284.8 eV. Point of Zero Charge (PZC) measurements were obtained following the method described by Nabais and Carrott [23]. For the determination of acid groups, 0.15 g of sample was mixed with 30 mL of 0.01 M NaOH, performing these experiments in triplicate. The mixture was stirred for 24 h at 25 °C, filtered, and the resulting filtered solution (20 mL) was titrated with 0.01 M nitric acid. For the quantification of basic groups, 0.15 g of sample was mixed with 30 mL of 0.01 M HNO_3 , and the mixture was stirred for 24 h at 25 °C, filtered, and the resulting filtered solution was titrated with 0.01 M NaOH. Phenolphthalein was used as indicator. Acid and basic sites were expressed as mEq/g. FT-IR spectra were recorded in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} on a THERMO spectrophotometer using KBr pellets or with ATR. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM): SEM images were obtained using QUANTA 3D FEG (FEI Company) with secondary electron detector, 15.0 kV acceleration voltage, and at high vacuum. Melting points were determined on an Electrothermal IA 9000 apparatus and are uncorrected. NMR spectra were recorded at 298 K on Bruker Ultrashield TM 500 Plus and Bruker Ultrashield TM 300 instruments. Samples were dissolved in $CDCl_3$ using tetramethylsilane (Me_4Si , TMS) ($\delta = 0.00$ ppm) as internal reference. Thin-layer

chromatography (TLC) was performed on aluminium sheets coated with 60 F₂₅₄ silica from Merck.

2.2. Sonochemical reactions

Reactions activated by ultrasound were performed using a JP Selecta ultrasound bath with a nominal frequency of 40 kHz. Calorimetry was employed as standard protocol to determine the acoustic power. The temperature of the bath, filled with distilled water, was measured with a thermometer. Ultrasonic power (P_U , in watts) was calculated as $P_U = (\Delta T/\Delta t)C_p \cdot m$, where $\Delta T/\Delta t$ denotes the rate of the temperature rise, C_p the specific heat capacity of water and m is the mass of water. The temperature rise was measured at different intervals spanning a period of 60 min. During this calibration cooling was not employed. The net average ultrasonic power dissipated in the medium was estimated to be 89 W. All reactions, either thermally or sonochemically activated, were performed in conventional Pyrex glass vials. For sonochemical reactions, vials were put inside cavitation intensifying bags (CIBs) obtained from BuBClean, The Netherlands, which were filled with distilled water, then immersed into the bath and irradiated for a given time at ambient temperature (25 °C). Temperature was kept constant (± 2 °C) with external ice. Medium-size bags (100 x 150 mm), 50 μm thick, were made of recycled PP (polypropylene) and are pitted in the inner surface. Pits through the microstructured bag have diameters between 100 and 500 μm and a depth of 100-200 μm . The CIBs have been used in previous sonochemical studies [24] (vide infra).

2.3. Synthesis of catalysts

2.3.1. Hydrothermal carbon from saccharose (**HT**).

A solution of saccharose (20 g in 50 mL of distilled water) was placed in a teflon vessel reinforced with a stainless-steel outer jacket. After a thermal treatment at 180 °C for 20 h, the solid was filtered, washed several times with water (200 mL), and dried at 110 °C for at least 8 h.

2.3.2. Hydrothermal carbon from saccharose treated with sulfuric acid (**HT-S**). Hydrothermal carbon (**HT**) was treated with concentrated H₂SO₄ (98%) at 25 °C for 90 min, using a ratio of 20 mL of acid per gram of carbon. The solid was rinsed with distilled water (until no sulfates were detected into the washings) and dried at 110 °C for at least 8 h.

2.4. Thermal syntheses of 1,3-dioxanes and solketal

2.4.1. 2,2,5,5-Tetramethyl-1,3-dioxane (**14**)

A mixture of 2,2-dimethylpropane-1,3-diol (0.5009 g), the catalyst **HT-S** (0.0250 g) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (5 mL) was placed in a sealed vial at 80 °C under stirring. After 50 min, the catalyst was filtered through a glass microfiber filter with a nylon membrane of 0.22 μm , and the resulting filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to give

1,3-dioxane **14** as a colorless oil (0.5651 g, 82%). IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ 1215, 1189, 1091, 1043 (C-O-C) cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.50 (s, 4H, 2x CH_2), 1.42 (s, 6H, 2x CH_3), 0.97 (s, 6H, 2x CH_3) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 97.8 ($[\text{CH}_3]_2\text{C}$), 70.8 (2x CH_2), 30.1 ($[\text{CH}_2]_2\text{C}$), 23.9 (2x CH_3), 22.7 (2x CH_3) ppm. HRMS-ESI ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$): calculated: 145.1223; found: 145.1196.

2.4.2. 5,5-Bis(bromomethyl)-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxane (**15**)

A mixture of 2,2-bis(bromomethyl)propane-1,3-diol (0.5028 g), the catalyst **HT-S** (0.0250 g) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (5 mL) was placed in a sealed vial at 80 °C under stirring. After 60 min, the catalyst was filtered through a glass microfiber filter with a nylon membrane of 0.22 μm , and the resulting filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to give 1,3-dioxane **15** as white crystalline solid (0.5709 g, 99%). M.p. 58-60 °C. IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ 1210, 1190, 1108, 1078, 1046 (C-O-C) cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.80 (s, 4H, 2x CH_2), 3.58 (s, 4H, 2x CH_2), 1.42 (s, 6H, 2x CH_3) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 99.1 ($[\text{CH}_3]_2\text{C}$), 65.0 (2x CH_2), 37.9 ($[\text{CH}_2]_4\text{C}$), 36.0 (2x CH_2), 23.6 (2x CH_3) ppm. HRMS-ESI ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{Br}_2\text{O}_2[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$): calculated: 300.9433; found: 300.9382.

2.4.3. 2,2-Dimethyl-5-pentyl-1,3-dioxane (**16**)

A mixture of 2-pentylpropane-1,3-diol (0.5153 g), the catalyst **HT-S** (0.0247 g) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (5 mL) was placed in a sealed vial at 80 °C under stirring. After 60 min, the catalyst was filtered through a glass microfiber filter with a nylon membrane of 0.22 μm , and the resulting filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was purified by flash column chromatography (hexane/ethyl acetate, 99:1) to give 1,3-dioxane **16** as a colorless oil (0.5024 g, 77%). IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ 1198, 1158, 1121, 1073 (C-O-C) cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.84 (dd, $J = 12.0$ Hz, $J = 4.5$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 3.56 (dd, $J = 12.0$ Hz, $J = 10.0$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 1.87-1.80 (m, 1H, CH), 1.43 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.40 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.32-1.26 (m, 6H, 3x CH_2), 1.17 (dd, $J = 13.5$ Hz, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 0.88 (t, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 3H, CH_3) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 97.9 ($[\text{CH}_3]_2\text{C}$), 65.2 (2x CH_2), 34.3 (CH), 32.1 (CH_2), 28.8 (CH_2), 27.8 (CH_3), 26.3 (CH_2), 22.6 (CH_2), 20.5 (CH_3), 14.2 (CH_3) ppm. HRMS-ESI ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_2[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$): calculated: 187.1693; found: 187.1672.

2.4.4. 5-Butyl-5-ethyl-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxane (**17**)

A mixture of 2-butyl-2-ethylpropane-1,3-diol (0.5111 g), the catalyst **HT-S** (0.0250 g) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (5 mL) was placed in a sealed vial at 80 °C under stirring. After 40 min, the catalyst was filtered through a glass microfiber filter with a nylon membrane of 0.22 μm , and the resulting filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was purified by flash column chromatography (hexane/ethyl acetate, 99:1) to give 1,3-dioxane **17** as a colorless oil (0.5192 g, 81%). IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ 1206, 1156, 1103, 1060 (C-O-C) cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.57 (d, $J = 11.5$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 3.54 (d, $J = 11.5$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 1.42 (c, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 1.40 (s, 6H, 2x CH_3), 1.33-1.27 (m, 4H, 2x CH_2), 1.19-1.13 (m, 2H, CH_2), 0.91 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 3H, CH_3), 0.81 (t, $J = 7.5$ Hz, 3H, CH_3) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 98.1 ($[\text{CH}_3]_2\text{C}$), 68.1 (2x CH_2), 35.0 ($[\text{CH}_2]_4\text{C}$), 31.3 (CH_2), 24.9 (CH_2), 24.3 (CH_2), 23.7 (CH_2), 23.6 (CH_3), 14.2 (CH_3), 7.3 (CH_3) ppm. HRMS-ESI ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{25}\text{O}_2[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$): calculated: 201.1849; found: 201.1829.

2.4.5. (2,2,5-Trimethyl-1,3-dioxan-5-yl)methanol (**18**) and 5-(((2-methoxypropan-2-yl)oxy)methyl)-2,2,5-trimethyl-1,3-dioxane (**21**)

A mixture of 2-(hydroxymethyl)-2-methylpropane-1,3-diol (0.5149 g), the catalyst **HT-S** (0.0247 g) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (5 mL) was placed in a sealed vial at 80 °C under stirring. After 45 min, the catalyst was filtered through a glass microfiber filter with a nylon membrane of 0.22 µm, and the resulting filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was purified by flash column chromatography (hexane/ethyl acetate gradient, from 99:1 to 60:40) to give 1,3-dioxanes **18** (0.3397 g, 50%) and **21** (0.4870 g, 49%).

(2,2,5-Trimethyl-1,3-dioxan-5-yl)methanol (**18**): IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ 3408 (O-H), 1207, 1151, 1082, 1046 (C-O-C) cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.69 (s, 2H, CH_2OH), 3.68 (d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, 2H, $2\times\text{CH}_2$), 3.61 (d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 1.45 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.40 (s, 3H, CH_3), 0.83 (s, 3H, CH_3) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 98.1 ($[\text{CH}_3]_2\text{C}$), 66.4 (CH_2), 66.0 (CH_2), 34.9 ($[\text{CH}_2]_2\text{C}$), 27.5 (CH_3), 20.2 (CH_3), 17.7 (CH_3) ppm. HRMS-ESI ($\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$): calculated: 161.1172; found: 161.1150.

5-(((2-Methoxypropan-2-yl)oxy)methyl)-2,2,5-trimethyl-1,3-dioxane (**21**): ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.72 (d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 3.55 (d, $J = 12.0$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 3.38 (s, 2H, CH_2), 3.21 (s, 3H, OCH_3), 1.43 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.40 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.34 (s, 6H, $2\times\text{CH}_3$), 0.89 (s, 3H, CH_3) ppm.

2.4.6. 3,3,9,9-Tetramethyl-2,4,8,10-tetraoxaspiro[5.5]undecane (**19**)

A mixture of 2,2-bis(hydroxymethyl)propane-1,3-diol (0.5028 g), the catalyst **HT-S** (0.0250 g) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (5 mL) was placed in a sealed vial at 80 °C under stirring. After 55 min, the catalyst was filtered through a glass microfiber filter with a nylon membrane of 0.22 µm, and the resulting filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to give bis(1,3-dioxane) **19** as white crystalline solid (0.7861 g, 99%). M.p. 109–111 °C. IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ 1197, 1166, 1152, 1098, 1053 (C-O-C) cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 3.74 (s, 8H, $4\times\text{CH}_2$), 1.40 (s, 12H, $4\times\text{CH}_3$) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 98.7 ($2\times[\text{CH}_3]_2\text{C}$), 64.2 ($4\times\text{CH}_2$), 32.7 ($[\text{CH}_2]_4\text{C}$), 23.7 ($4\times\text{CH}_3$) ppm. HRMS-ESI ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_4[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$): calculated: 217.1434; found: 217.1410.

2.4.7. 5-(2-(2,4-Difluorophenyl)allyl)-2,2-dimethyl-1,3-dioxane (**20**)

A mixture of 2-(2-(2,4-difluorophenyl)allyl)propane-1,3-diol (0.5162 g), the catalyst **HT-S** (0.0252 g) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (5 mL) was placed in a sealed vial at 80 °C under stirring. After 35 min, the catalyst was filtered through a glass microfiber filter with a nylon membrane of 0.22 µm, and the resulting filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was purified by flash column chromatography (hexane/ethyl acetate, 99:1) to give 1,3-dioxane **20** as a solid (0.4234, 71%). M.p. 52–54 °C. IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ 1632 (C=C), 1615, 1591, 1499, 1455 (arom), 1199, 1135, 1088, 1067, 1055 (C-O-C) cm^{-1} . ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.20 (dt, $J = 8.5$ Hz, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H, H-arom), 6.86–6.77 (m, 2H, H-arom), 5.24 (s, 1H, CH), 5.18 (s, 1H, CH), 3.80 (dd, $J = 11.5$ Hz, $J = 4.5$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 3.58 (dd, $J = 11.5$ Hz, $J = 8.5$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 2.43 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 2H, CH_2), 1.83–1.75 (m, 1H, CH), 1.42 (s, 3H, CH_3), 1.37 (s, 3H, CH_3) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 162.4 (dd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 247.5$ Hz, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 12.0$ Hz, C-arom), 160.0 (dd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 248.5$ Hz, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 11.5$ Hz, C-arom), 141.2 (C=), 130.8 (dd, $J_{\text{C-F}} = 9.5$ Hz, $J_{\text{C-F}} =$

6.0 Hz, CH-arom), 125.2 (dd, $J_{C-F} = 14.5$ Hz, $J_{C-F} = 3.5$ Hz, C-arom), 118.1 (CH₂=), 111.4 (dd, $J_{C-F} = 20.5$ Hz, $J_{C-F} = 3.5$ Hz, C-arom), 104.3 (t, $J_{C-F} = 26.0$ Hz, C-arom), 98.0 ([CH₃]₂C), 64.5, (2xCH₂), 36.1 (CH₂), 32.5 (CH), 26.8 (CH₃), 21.3 (CH₃) ppm. Elemental analysis, calculated for C₁₅H₁₈F₂O₂ (268.30): C, 67.15; H, 6.76. Found: C, 67.40; H, 6.82.

2.4.8. 2,2-Dimethyl-4-hydroxymethyl-1,3-dioxolane (solketal, **6**)

A mixture of propane-1,2,3-triol (0.5055 g), the catalyst **HT-S** (0.0250 g) and 2,2-dimethoxypropane (5 mL) was placed in a sealed vial at 25 °C under stirring. After 3.5 h, the catalyst was filtered through a glass microfiber filter with a nylon membrane of 0.22 μm, and the resulting filtrate was concentrated under reduced pressure to give solketal **6** as a colorless oil (0.6883, 95%). IR (ATR) $\bar{\nu}_{\max}$ 3419 (O-H), 1211, 1156, 1046 (C-O-C) cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 4.27-4.22 (m, 1H, CH), 4.04 (dd, $J = 8.5$ Hz, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 1H, CH₂), 3.79 (dd, $J = 8.5$ Hz, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 1H, CH₂), 3.73 (dd, $J = 12.0$ Hz, $J = 3.0$ Hz, 1H, CH₂), 3.60 (dd, $J = 12.0$ Hz, $J = 4.5$ Hz, 1H, CH₂), 2.22 (s, 1H, OH), 1.45 (s, 3H, CH₃), 1.38 (s, 3H, CH₃) ppm. ¹³C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 109.5 ([CH₃]₂C), 76.3 (CH), 65.8 (CH₂), 63.1 (CH₂), 26.8 (CH₃), 25.4 (CH₃) ppm. HRMS-ESI (C₆H₁₃O₃[M+H]⁺): calculated: 133.0859; found: 133.0900.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Synthesis and characterization of catalysts

As stated above, two acid carbons were investigated in this work to evaluate their catalytic activity in the acetalization reaction of a range of diols. Both catalysts were prepared through a hydrothermal procedure consisting of heating an aqueous solution of saccharose at 180 °C for 20 h. The catalyst **HT** was subsequently treated with concentrated sulfuric acid at 25 °C for 90 min to afford the sulfonated derivative (**HT-S**), which was proved to be superior in terms of catalytic activity.

The porosity of **HT** and **HT-S** was studied through N₂ adsorption isotherms (Figure 4). Both carbons showed low adsorption capacity, indicative of an almost negligible porous development, in contrast to other activated carbons employed in this type of reactions, for which specific surfaces of above 1000 m² g⁻¹ were determined [25].

Figure 4. Evolution of catalyst porosity as measured by N₂ adsorption isotherms of **HT** and **HT-S**.

Table 1 collects specific surface values after applying the BET model [26], as well as the volume of micropores (V_{mic}) and mesopores (V_{mes}). As expected, these catalysts also show low volume values of micropores and mesopores.

Table 1. Specific surfaces (S_{BET}), volume of micropores (V_{mic}) and mesopores (V_{mes}).

Catalyst	S_{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	V_{mic} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	V_{mes} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)
HT	27	0.001	0.025
HT-S	0.031	0.001	0.025

Elemental analysis (Table 2) confirms that carbon is the main component for both solids. Moreover, treatment with sulfuric acid leads to an increase in sulfur and oxygen contents, in agreement with the oxidation of the pristine carbon **HT** and concomitant formation of sulfonic groups on the surface.

Table 2. Elemental analysis of **HT** and **HT-S**.

Catalyst	C (%)	H (%)	S (%)	O (%)*
HT	64.30	6.66	0.01	29.03
HT-S	59.59	3.19	3.41	33.81

* Obtained by difference.

Surficial elemental composition of **HT** and **HT-S** was studied by XPS (Table 3, Figure S1). The main component is again carbon in both cases. On the other hand, oxygen content is high for both solids, a fact consistent with a mild carbonization process that maintains many functional groups coming from saccharose. Furthermore, chemical treatment with sulfuric acid increases once more the amount of sulfur and oxygen. Thus, the peak at 168 eV in the S 2p spectrum is assigned to oxidized forms of sulfur such as sulfonic groups, which should be attached to the surface of the catalyst.

Table 3. Elemental composition of **HT** and **HT-S** by XPS.

Catalyst	C (%)	O (%)	S (%)
HT	78.01	21.99	--
HT-S	73.75	24.62	1.63

Point of zero charge (PZC) values and quantification of acid groups are gathered in Table 4. Hydrothermal carbon **HT** is very acid. Moreover, treatment with sulfuric acid increases the acid character through a lower PZC, consistent with the formation of sulfonic groups grafted on the surface. It is worth noting that acids groups could not be determined for **HT-S** due to its high acidity. Similarly, basic groups could not be determined for both solids either.

Table 4. PZC values and acid groups of catalysts.

Catalyst	PZC	Acid groups (mEq g ⁻¹)
HT	2.8	1.96
HT-S	1.9	ND*

* Not determined due to the high acidity of the solid.

FT-IR spectra of **HT** and **HT-S** exhibit broad absorption bands above 3000 cm⁻¹, corresponding to hydroxyl groups (Figure S2). Furthermore, bands attributable to double bonds C=C and C=O are also observed in the spectra about 1600-1700 cm⁻¹. Likewise, the presence of sulfonic groups on **HT-S** is confirmed by two bands detected at 1167 and 638 cm⁻¹ [27].

SEM images show a similar morphology for both catalysts based on spheres with a smooth surface (Figure 5), confirming that the chemical treatment with sulfuric acid does not modify the morphology of the solids.

Figure 5. SEM images of **HT** [(a) and (b)] and **HT-S** [(c) and (d)].

3.2. Thermal protection of diols

As described above, catalysts **HT** and **HT-S** exhibited a remarkable acid character with PZC values of 2.9 and 1.8, thereby expecting them to behave as good catalysts for the protection reaction of a range of diols as isopropylidene ketals (Scheme 1). These reactions were conducted in a sealed vial using 5% of the catalyst (with respect to the mass of the starting diol) at 80 °C (Table 5). These conditions have been previously optimized [25].

Scheme 1. Protection of 1,3-diols with **HT** and **HT-S**.

Table 5. Acetalization of diols with **HT** and **HT-S** at 80 °C.

Entry	Substrate	Catalyst	Time	Yield
1	8	No catalyst	24 h	NR ^a
2	12	No catalyst	24 h	NR
3	13	No catalyst	24 h	NR
4	8	HT	7 d	NR
5	12	HT	7 d	91% ^b
6	12	HT	2.0 h	NR
7	7	HT-S	0.8 h	82% ^b
8	8	HT-S	1.0 h	99% ^b
9	9	HT-S	1.0 h	77% ^c
10	10	HT-S	0.7 h	81% ^c
11	11	HT-S	0.8 h	50% ^c
12	12	HT-S	1.0 h	99% ^b
13	13	HT-S	23 h	71% ^c

^a No reaction (product not isolated). ^b Isolated yield without purification by column chromatography. ^c Isolated yield after purification by column chromatography.

Data from Table 5 evidence that the reaction requires catalysis (entries 1-3). On the other hand, only one reaction performed with **HT** led to the desired product, though with a long reaction time (entry 5). Catalyst **HT-S**, however, allowed in general isolation of

acetonides with good yields and short reaction times, except for 1,3-dioxane **18** from **11**, due to the isolation of 1,3-dioxane **21** as a mixed ketal (Scheme 2) as well.

Scheme 2. Acetalization of triol **11** at 80 °C with **HT-S**.

As mentioned in the introductory remarks, protection of glycerol was a primary goal, given the current need for valorizing and/or upgrading this side product from biorefineries. Glycerol protection was then carried out under the same conditions, which leads however to a 1:1 mixture of five- and six-membered cyclization products, namely solketal (**6**) and 1,3-dioxane **23**, respectively (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Acetalization of glycerol at 80 °C with **HT-S**.

The above results clearly demonstrate that the most promising catalyst for the protection of diols should be the sulfonated hydrothermal carbon **HT-S**. Such a behavior can be explained by the presence of sulfonic groups on the surface enhancing the catalytic activity. We reasoned that in terms of energy consumption, reactions conducted at lower temperatures would be desirable and selectivity could eventually be improved. This kinetic control could take place at the expense of lower conversions, nevertheless. Accordingly, diol protection was reassessed at 50 °C and ambient temperature (25 °C) as gathered in Table 6.

Table 6. Acetalization of diols catalyzed by **HT-S** at milder temperatures.

Entry	Substrate	Product	Time	Temperature	Yield
1	7	14	27 h	50 °C	75% ^a
2	7	14	72 h	25 °C	56% ^a
3	8	15	26 h	50 °C	96% ^a
4	8	15	72 h	25 °C	99% ^a
5	9	16	72 h	50 °C	52% ^b

6	9	16	96 h	25 °C	97% ^a
7	10	17	21 h	50 °C	75% ^b
8	10	17	25 h	25 °C	95% ^a
9	12	19	7.0 h	50 °C	97% ^a
10	12	19	48 h	25 °C	84% ^a
11	13	20	3.5 h	50 °C	70% ^b
12	13	20	24 h	25 °C	95% ^a

^a Isolated yield without purification by column chromatography. ^b Isolated yield after purification by column chromatography.

As expected, reactions took longer as the temperature decreases. Gratifyingly, the best yields were obtained when reactions were performed at 25 °C and avoiding chromatographic purification in all cases. This suggests that mild conditions enable cleaner transformations and are less prone to either decomposition or formation of side products. In any case, acetalization of triol **11** at 25 and 50 °C still drove to mixtures of ketals **18** and **21**. However, the reaction with glycerol at 25 °C catalyzed by **HT-S**, resulted in the valuable isolation of 1,3-dioxolane solketal (**6**) with excellent yield (95%) and without chromatographic purification.

3.3. Ultrasound-assisted protection of diols

In line with our research and educational purposes in adopting enabling technologies, it became natural to us the application of ultrasound to this heterogeneous catalytic diol protection. Although, in global terms, a sonochemical reaction can be categorized as a *thermally-allowed reaction* (sound is partially dissipated as heat), sonication supplies largely *mechanical input* through microbubble collapse in liquids. Thus, the paradigm-shifted concept is that a mechanical force can overcome the energy barrier associated with either bond-forming or bond-breaking steps as much as thermal energy does [28]. Relative to solvent-free reactions, however, mechanical activation in liquids is difficult to achieve at a large extent. Cavitation effects provided by shear forces and shock waves can be noticeable and magnified near solid particles [29].

As already mentioned, sonication can be conducted in an affordable cleaning bath using micropitted cavitation bags, as illustrated in Figures 6 and 7, which have been successfully employed in heterogeneous catalysis [24]. Such bags are designed in a way that cavitation effects are substantially increased. Pits behave actually as microreactors improving local mixing and breaking up particles more efficiently than other conventional sonoreactors. Within the range of frequencies employed, 37 kHz was reported to be the optimal value to achieve the lowest treatment time [30], which lies in the typical frequencies of cleaning bath transducers. Remarkably, the simple devices are proven to

be reliable enough as similar results were obtained at different laboratories using different cleaning sonoreactors [31].

Figure 6. Experimental set-up employed in sonochemical catalysis. Vials containing the reaction mixture are placed in a water-filled cavitation intensification bag, fixed inside an ultrasonic bath.

Figure 7. Schematic representation of the effect of cavitation intensifying bags (BuBble[®] bags) in heterogeneous catalysis. Inside: the sulfonated carbocatalyst and the adsorbed organic species are expected to undergo rapid mechanical and thermal activation. Adapted with permission from the literature [24], open-access publication under Creative Commons Licence.

A priori, a sonochemical transformation at high temperature is to be discouraged. Any increase in temperature will raise the vapor pressure and this occurs together with a decrease in solvent viscosity and surface tension. Under such conditions cavitation will be easier, but less violent [32]. In the present case, even if high performance has been obtained at 80 °C, reactions are carried out in the absence of solvent and using 2,2-dimethoxypropane as both solvent and ketalization reagent, whose boiling point is 83 °C. In line with the above premise, near the boiling point the rapid formation of more microbubbles will significantly attenuate ultrasound propagation and cavitation implosion is less energy efficient. On the other hand, the catalyzed acetalization of diols follows a polar mechanism and will therefore be scarcely sensitive to pure chemical effects derived from cavitation, whereas physical events should be enhanced. Silent reactions at 50 °C are rapid yet, albeit chromatographic purification is required as noted above, which suggests side transformations. To this end, ultrasound-activated reactions were attempted at 25 °C seeking both clean and selective processes. A sealed vial (Figure 6) containing the reaction mixture was placed into a cavitation intensifying bag using a 5% (with respect to the mass of the starting diol) of the catalyst **HT-S** (Scheme 4). Initial assays were conducted in the absence of bags in order to check the actual effect, if any, of this modification. Both direct immersion of vials into the liquid and placing them in an empty pitted bag followed by irradiation, resulted in significant acceleration relative to thermal reactions, thus evidencing the positive effect of mechanical activation provided by ultrasound. Yet, sonication times could further be shortened by half if bags are filled with water prior to irradiation. This points to a membrane-like effect, where micropits channel sound waves more efficiently throughout the liquid medium. Experimental data for reactions gone to completion are collected in Table 7.

Scheme 4. Ultrasound-activated protection of diols with **HT-S**.

Table 7. Ultrasound-activated reactions catalyzed by **HT-S**.

Entry	Substrate	Product	Time	Yield ^a
1	7	14	6.0 h	75%
2	9	16	2.0 h	97%
3	10	17	1.0 h	98%
4	12	19	1.7 h	94%
5	13	20	0.5 h	97%

^aIsolated yield without purification by column chromatography.

Compared to silent reactions performed at 25 and 50 °C, improved results were in general obtained in terms of reaction times and conversions. Diol **7** afforded its acetonide **14** after 6 h-irradiation, yet significantly shorter than thermal reactions leading to completion and taking from 24 to 72 h. Diols **9**, **10**, **12** and **13** gave rise to essentially quantitative isolated yields within 1-2 h or less (Table 7). Notably, no purification by column chromatography was required at all, thus unveiling an expeditious clean transformation. Protection of diol **8**, however, could not be completed after 6 h, although a 67:33 mixture of product **15** and the corresponding intermediate was isolated (see Sect. 3.6, Scheme 5). Triol **11** led, as observed under thermal activation, to a mixture of 1,3-dioxanes **18** and **21** in 56:44 ratio. Even if a smooth transformation was observed for glycerol, contrary to the silent reaction at 25 °C leading exclusively to solketal (**6**), the ultrasonic reaction produced both the desired dioxolane solketal and the corresponding dioxane (**6:23** in a 60:40 mixture).

At this stage, we consider that sonication outperforms the catalyzed acetalization with respect to conventional conditions. Although the focused radiation channeled by the micropitted bag has been shown to be exceedingly large [30], the actual acoustic power delivered into such a complex heterogeneous system is uncertain, which should also be dependent on the frequency and gas content. However, such correlations mostly come from studies on homogeneous reactions [33]. A recent analysis, however, suggests that the ultrasonic power, measured by calorimetry, is not influenced by the presence of solids in heterogeneous mixtures, and the dissipated radiation remains largely unchanged [34].

3.4. Catalyst Recyclability

Solvent and catalyst recycling are compulsory issues in sustainable chemistry. Recycling experiments were conducted for the harsh thermal conditions, at 80 °C for 60 min, using the protection of polyol **12**, as model compound, with the hydrothermal catalyst **HT-S**. After that time the catalyst was filtered and dried at 120 °C overnight. Table 8 shows that the catalyst can be reused up to 6 times with no loss of efficacy, maintaining excellent yields in all runs without purification by column chromatography.

Table 8. Recycling experiments with **HT-S**.

Run	Isolated yield
1	96%
2	97%
3	98%
4	93%
5	99%
6	98%

3.5. Structural elucidation of 1,3-dioxanes

The structure of 1,3-dioxanes was corroborated by analytical and spectroscopic techniques. FT-IR spectra (Figures S3-S10) showed no absorption bands above 3000 cm^{-1} , except for 1,3-dioxane **18**, that displayed one band at 3408 cm^{-1} due to the OH group (Figure S7). Bands corresponding to C-O-C stretching at $1040\text{-}1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were also detected, consistent with the presence of 1,3-dioxane rings. Moreover, ketal **20** also exhibited typical bands due to the aromatic ring, in the range $1500\text{-}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, as well as the absorption assigned to the exocyclic double bond at 1632 cm^{-1} (Figure S9).

NMR spectra showed characteristic signals for isopropylidene ketals (Figures S11-S26). ^{13}C NMR spectra displayed one peak at 100 ppm for 1,3-dioxanes, corresponding to the quaternary carbon of the isopropylidene group. This carbon resonated at 109.5 ppm for the 1,3-dioxolane **6** (Figure S26). Elemental analysis and HRMS were also consistent with the described structures.

3.6. Kinetic studies

Finally, we also carried out a kinetic analysis based on proton NMR monitoring for the protection of diol **5**. Thus, aliquots were taken from the reaction mixture at different times, filtered and concentrated. Further analysis by NMR allowed the quantification of intermediate **I₈₋₁₅** and ketal **15** (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5. Acetalization of diol **8** with HT-S.

Given the velocity of protection at ambient temperature under sonication, Figure 8 shows the evolution of intermediate **I₈₋₁₅** and ketal **15** at 80 and 50 °C, respectively, in order to determine kinetic evolution with accuracy. Diol **8** is consumed rapidly in both cases and the 1,3-dioxane **15** is obtained quantitatively after 60 min (at 80 °C) and 24 h (at 50 °C). A first-order rate constant of 2.07 s^{-1} was determined at 50 °C for the evolution of intermediate **I₈₋₁₅** (Figure S27).

Figure 8. NMR monitoring of diol **8** with HT-S at 80 °C (left) and at 50 °C (right).

4. Conclusions

We have shown the benefits of performing the acid-catalyzed acetalization of 1,3-diols under sonication at ambient temperature, relative to thermal reactions conducted at higher temperatures. A heterogeneous, eco-compatible saccharose-based hydrothermal carbocatalyst demonstrated to be highly efficient. The polar mechanism is enhanced by focused irradiation through micropitted cavitation intensifying bags using a cleaning bath. The comparative analysis with thermal processes, indicates that under ultrasound high-yielding reactions take place and reaction times can be cut down to a few hours, whereas they take longer, up to 24 h at 80 °C, 72 h at 50 °C, and up to 96 h at 25 °C. Remarkably, reactions at 25 °C (both thermal and sonicated) proceeded smoothly without requiring product purification by chromatography, unlike reactions at either 50 °C or 80 °C. This research study does not only show the adaptation of a classical transformation to a more environmentally benign protocol, but also illustrates a pedagogical framework suitable for other synthetic transformations. These results establish a learning mode where current research involving the design and implementation of green heterogeneous catalysts are supplemented through the application of a non-conventional technology, namely sonochemistry, usually ignored in postgraduate curricula and research portfolios.

Given the interdisciplinary character of sonochemistry, in the field of sonochemistry education, it is essential to provide a rigorous and robust foundation of physico-chemical principles. This approach should impart students and newcomers with core concepts, while equipping them with the necessary skills to apply this knowledge in varied pursuits. Since synthetic chemistry represents a cornerstone of applied sciences, by integrating practical laboratory work in sonochemistry with organic synthesis (the latter embracing goals such as sustainability, efficiency or catalysis), sonochemistry education will more efficiently address global challenges in academia and industry.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

R.F.M.: Conceptualization, investigation, supervision, draft elaboration, funding acquisition, writing, review and editing. **A.M.E.:** methodology and investigation. **R.P.B.:** methodology, investigation, supervision. **C.J.D.V.:** investigation, funding acquisition, writing and review. **M.A.P.:** methodology, investigation, supervision. **D.F.R.:** investigation, funding acquisition, writing, review and editing. **P.C.:** investigation, supervision, draft elaboration, writing, review and editing.

Declaration of competing interest

D.F.R. is a founder and a scientific advisor of BuBclean, a Dutch start-up company that commercializes the BuBble Bags (Cavitation Intensifying Bags - CIB) and operates in the ultrasonic cleaning solutions market.

The other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interest and/or personal implications that might have influenced the work described through this article.

Data Availability

Data will be made available upon reasonable request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.20xx.xxxxxx>.

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